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A PUBLIC HEALTH PERSPECTIVE OF A DECADE OF RESEARCH ON MYCOTOXIN CONTAMINATION OF CEREAL FOOD AND ASSOCIATED HEALTH RISKS

Ljilja Torović^{1,2*}

¹Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, University of Novi Sad, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

²Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Futoška 121, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

*Corresponding author:

E-mail address: ljilja.torovic@mf.uns.ac.rs

From a public health perspective, mycotoxins in food are chronic risk factors in the human diet, with the potential to exert extremely diverse adverse health effects. Cereals, the staple food, are susceptible to the growth of miscellaneous fungi, which produce various mycotoxins. Food contaminated with mycotoxins is unsafe and therefore not food – is that always the case? Data related to mycotoxin contamination of more than 300 cereal products (flour, bread, breakfast cereals, pasta, crackers, biscuits) obtained from multi-year sampling campaigns carried out during the last decade on the market of Vojvodina (obtained by standard liquid chromatography analyzes) were collated and combined with national food consumption data in order to assess the extent of human exposure and consequent threat to public health. The overview of the occurrence data revealed a fairly high frequency of most of the principal mycotoxins, but in low concentrations, except in years marked by drastic climatic conditions during sensitive periods of crop vegetation: hot and dry as opposed to cold and rainy caused contamination with aflatoxins versus fusarium toxins. Regarding the chronic health risk, mycotoxins other than aflatoxins (ochratoxin A, zearalenone, deoxynivalenol, fumonisins) did not pose concerns in any of the population groups, despite the non-compliance of a number of samples with food safety regulations. On the other hand, comparison of the aflatoxin exposure with respective toxicological threshold caused uneasiness, especially in case of toddlers, children and adolescents, while among adults the highest exposure was noted in vegetarians. The findings were similar for regular cereal foods and those labelled as gluten-free. Further concerns relate to aggregate (one mycotoxin from multiple dietary sources consumed in relevant time-frame) as well as cumulative exposure (multiple mycotoxins simultaneously from one or more dietary sources). To effectively protect public health, evidence-based risk prioritization should be incorporated into the national food safety system.

Keywords: aflatoxins, ochratoxin A, zearalenone, deoxynivalenol, fumonisins, risk assessment